

Experiment on elicitation of context-aware features

May 2021

Have you ever heard of
“context-aware features“?

- Context-aware functionalities are functionalities that consider context to produce a certain system behavior, typically an adaptation or recommendation.

Example 1: YouTube (adaptation)

Example 2: Gmail (recommendation)

Early RE: context modeling

DORFFUNK

VIDEO

Today's experiment

To participate in this restricted survey, you need a valid token.

If you have been issued a token, please enter it in the box below and click continue.

* Token:

Continue

C5.2 - Experiment with practitioners

Welcome to the activity on elicitation of context-aware features. This is a controlled experiment and the participation is anonymous.

Confidentiality: To help protect your confidentiality, this instrument does not contain any information that could personally identify you. All data will be stored in a password-protected location. Your responses will be kept confidential. The anonymized data will be available to all researchers involved in this project. The raw data collected will not be shared with third parties at any time. Any insights gained will be used in the context of doctoral research. This may also include publication of the results (including aggregation of responses) in scientific publications. The raw data will be deleted as soon as it is no longer needed for the stated purposes, but no later than at the end of the doctoral research.

I consent to participate.

Next

Download here the artifact (PDF)

After the download, please open the file in a new window.

Then, click on NEXT in this page.

 If you have problems downloading and/or opening this PDF file, please contact the moderator.

Next

Write down a requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task

Next

***Is there still time?**

! Choose one of the following answers

YES!

No, time is over.

Next

Write down another requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task

Next

***Is there still time?**

! Choose one of the following answers

YES!

No, time is over.

Next

1. There is NO right or wrong in this activity; just do it as good as you can.
2. There is NO minimum number of requirements that you have to create.
3. Once you finish a requirement, move to the next.

30 minutes

And the user task to be improved via context awareness is...

CREATE A COMMENT

Mike takes his phone and launches DorfFunk to check out what is new in his community

He sees the post of Lena in the feed. She is asking for information about bakeries in the town. Mike clicks on it

Mike reads all comments and an idea for Lena comes to his mind

He starts to write a comment

Mike also wants to add some pictures of the bread that he did by himself last weekend

He selects the pictures from the gallery

He checks the pictures

**Mike finishes
writing his
comment and sends
it**

How to improve this user task with context awareness?

- Remember of the task in focus: CREATE A COMMENT
- Remember to use the context model that you will receive

Write requirements as specific as possible

- Depending on the network connection of the user, the system shall adapt the video quality automatically. (bad example)
- When the network connection of the user has LOW BANDWIDTH, set the video quality to LOW automatically (good example)

How to use the context model that
you will receive to support your
activity in the experiment

A data-driven context model

- Today, you will receive a context model that was created using a data-driven process.
- Data from the application in focus in the experiment was analyzed to generate the context model.
- The context model contains contexts that were found to be relevant (by the data-driven process) for a certain user task of interest.

This is what the structure of the context model looks like:

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This is the basic structure. It is always present.
It describes how the context is (typically) when the user performs the task.

This is what the structure of the context model looks like:

Optionally, this part may be present sometimes. It complements the description with additional contextual information.

Example

- Imagine that YouTube does not implement automatic adjustment of video quality based on the user's network connection.
- When the network connection is slow, users manually adjust the video quality to "LOW" in order to watch their videos without interruptions.
- YouTube data is analyzed and the user behavior described above is identified. The context model could look like this:

Another example

- In the previous example, there were only two contextual elements: the network connection speed and the video quality. Let's imagine another example, with more contextual elements.
- In a car sharing app, users who are already using the cars sometimes want to *update the end-time* (task) of their rides.
- Data from the car sharing app is analyzed and certain contexts are found to be relevant when the user performs the task.
- The context model could look like this (see next slide):

Context model (car sharing app example)

- Each “path” represents a context. In this example, two contexts were identified.

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- Each “path” represents a context. In this example, two contexts were identified.
- The first path indicates that “when the current weather is snow storm and the distance between the car location and the return spot is not short, then the user (typically) updates the end-time”.

Context model (car sharing example)

- Each “path” represents a context. In this example, two contexts were identified.
- The first path indicates that “when the current weather is snow storm and the distance between the car location and the return spot is not short, then the user (typically) updates the end-time”.
- The second path indicates that “when the fuel level is between 2% and 19% (i.e., somewhat low) and the distance between the car location and the return spot is not short, then the user (typically) updates the end-time”.

Size of the context model

- Depending on how many contextual elements are involved in the analysis, and also on how many relevant contexts are found by the data-driven process, the context model will vary in size.
- In any case, starting from the node **WHEN**, each path corresponds to a relevant context found by the data-driven process.

Final remark

Notice that the data-driven context model does not give you requirements; it only tells you how the context might influence the user task (according to the data-driven analysis).

From the model to requirements: Example 1

- What does this context (path) say?
 - “When the network connection is < 1Mbps, then the user watches the video with LOW video quality”
- This is not a requirement, but a fact observed via the data
- Possible requirements based on this context:
 - R1 (adaptation): “When the network connection of the user is slow (1Mbps), the system shall adapt the video quality to LOW automatically”
 - R2 (recommendation): “When the network connection of the user is slow (<1Mbps), the system shall ask the user whether they want to reduce the quality of the video in order to prevent interruptions”

From the model to requirements: Example 2

- What does this context (path) say?
 - “When the fuel level is between 2% and 19% (i.e., somewhat low) and the distance between the car location and the return spot is not short, then the user (typically) updates the end-time
- Possible requirements based on this context:
 - R1 (recommendation): “When the fuel level is low and the distance between car location and return spot is not short, the system shall send a notification to the user phone telling them to consider updating the end-time of their ride.”
 - R2 (recommendation): “When the fuel level below 20% and the distance between car location and return spot is not short, the system shall send a notification to the user phone telling them to that fuel is low and suggesting them to postpone the end-time of their car for 30 minutes.”

From the model to requirements: Example 3

- What does this context (path) say?
 - “When the user is a man, then the user watches the video with LOW video quality”
- Possible requirements based on this context:
 - Non-sense!!

Use the context model to create requirements

- You will receive a context model that was generated by the data-driven process to support your elicitation task today.
- Use it as your source to identify new requirements as described in the previous examples – of course, only if the contexts included in the model are considered meaningful/relevant by you.

Here you go